

Steric effect in regioselective hydrostannation of alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates with triphenyltin hydride

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Abstract : Triphenyltin hydride under radical condition reacts with alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates to give hydrostannated products, where the stannyl group enters at α -position. Again, with increase in the bulkiness of alkoxy group product yield is decreased.

Keywords : Triphenyltin, hydrostannation, alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates.

Introduction

The hydrostannation of an olefinic double bond by an organotin hydride can provide a versatile way of preparing alkytin compounds as important intermediates in synthetic organic chemistry^{1,2}. Although the hydrostannation of alkynes has been widely studied, there has been relatively little investigation on the hydrostannation of alkenes using triphenyltin hydride. Hydrostannation with olefinic double bond under free radical condition results in the formation of stannyl derivatives¹⁻⁶. In palladium catalyzed reactions of tributyltin hydride with α,β -unsaturated nitriles the stannyl group is reported to have entered at α -position⁷ while with stannylcuprates β -addition of the moiety is reported⁸. In our investigation, when reacted with triphenyltin hydride under radical condition, alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates underwent hydrostannation at α -position (Scheme 1). Again it is observed that with increase in the bulkiness of alkoxy group product yield is decreased.

R = Me, Et, Bn; R¹ = Me, Et, *n*-Pr

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Our initial synthetic goal was to prepare alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates, which, should lead to the desired hydrostannation product. Olefins shown in Table 1 were prepared by coupling 2-methoxybenzaldehyde with a suitable phosphonium salt following the procedure of Wittig methodology⁹⁻¹³. In Table 1 results of hydrostannation of different olefins are recorded¹⁴. Out of the seven reactions, in two cases (Table 1, entry 1 and 2) high yields of hydrostannated product was observed. In others (Entry 3 to 7) low to moderate yields of hydrostannated products could be isolated. When reacted with triphenyltin hydride under radical condition, alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates undergo

Table 1. Reactions of triphenyltin hydride with α,β -unsaturated esters

Entry	R	R ₁	Product	Yield (mol %)
1	Me	Me	1a	80
2	Me	Et	1b	72
3	Me	<i>n</i> -Pr	1c	45
4	Et	Me	1d	25
5	Et	Et	1e	35
6	Bn	Me	1f	45
7	Bn	Et	1g	30

hydrostannation at α -position this was established by single crystal X-ray diffraction. In these reactions with low yields tin hydride was mostly degraded to highly insoluble byproducts, probably hexaphenylditin, and starting esters were mostly left unreacted. Therefore it may be confirmed that due to the increased bulkiness of the alkyl group hydrostannation of *o*-alkoxycinnamates is influenced.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in an electrical melting point apparatus (Scientific Device, India, and Type MP-D in open capillary) and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded with a FT-IR model Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RX 1 FT-IR system either as a thin film over KBr plate or as KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded either on a Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer or a Varian 400 MHz spectrometer in CDCl_3 as the solvent using TMS as the internal reference.

*Reactions of triphenyltin hydride with α,β -unsaturated esters (Scheme 1)*⁹: A solution of the α,β -unsaturated ester (1 equiv.) in dry benzene (5 mL/mmol) was degassed with dry nitrogen for 15 min followed by addition of the tin hydride (1.2 equiv.) and AIBN (5 mg) dissolve in dry benzene (2 mL/mmol of tin hydride). The mixture was refluxed under nitrogen and monitored by TLC. When the reaction was complete or appeared to have reached equilibrium the reaction mixture was allowed to cool, solvent removed under reduced pressure and the product was purified by column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh) and a mixture of petroleum ether (40–60 °C) and diethyl ether as the eluent.

Spectral data of the hydrostannated products are :

(i) *Methyl 3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1a)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 446, 670, 699, 737, 755, 842, 995, 1030, 1029, 1074, 1113, 1146, 1210, 1245, 1306, 1350, 1428, 1459, 1492, 1597, 1704, 2837, 2944, 3033; ^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 3.1–3.3 (5H, complex m, OMe and CH_2), 3.35–3.40 (1H, dd, CH), 3.71 (3H, s, OMe), 6.7–6.8 and 7.0–7.2 (4H, m, aromatic), 7.3–7.6 (15H, m, SnPh_3).

(ii) *Ethyl 3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1b)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 443, 498, 698, 731, 756, 801, 1024, 1067, 1101, 1149, 1209, 1239, 1260, 1297, 1337, 1366, 1428, 1491, 1592, 1687, 1734, 2960, 3048;

^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 0.7 (3H, t, Me), 3.6 (3H, s, OMe), 3.7–3.8 (3H, complex m, CH and CH_2), 6.6–6.7 (2H, m, aromatic), 6.9–7.1 (2H, m, aromatic), 7.3–7.5 (15H, m, SnPh_3).

(iii) *n-Propyl 3-(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1c)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 443, 610, 697, 730, 931, 1027, 1070, 1111, 1145, 1211, 1244, 1305, 1352, 1386, 1462, 1484, 1595, 1708, 2832, 2920, 2950, 3058; ^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 0.63 (3H, t, Me), 0.85–1.28 (5H, complex m, aliphatic), 3.1–3.6 (7H, complex m, aliphatic), 6.7–7.2 (4H, m, aromatic), 7.3–7.7 (15H, m, SnPh_3).

(iv) *Methyl 3-(*o*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1d)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 441, 503, 552, 696, 831, 885, 920, 964, 988, 1023, 1044, 1072, 1111, 1151, 1184, 1219, 1305, 1346, 1385, 1425, 1472, 1595, 1701, 2910, 2950, 2989, 3048, 3411; ^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 1.42 (3H, t, 3J 6.4 Hz, C-Me), 3.7–3.8 (6H, complex m, CO_2Me , CH and CH_2), 4.0 (2H, q, 3J 6.4 Hz, OCH_2), 6.6–7.8 (19H, complex m, aromatic).

(v) *Ethyl 3-(*o*-ethoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1e)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 503, 552, 831, 885, 920, 964, 988, 1023, 1044, 1072, 1111, 1151, 1184, 1219, 1305, 1346, 1425, 1472, 1595, 1701, 2910, 2950, 2989, 3048, 3411; ^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 0.85 (3H, t, CH_3), 1.29 (3H, t, CH_3), 3.1–4.1 (7H, complex m, 3CH_2 and CH), 6.7–6.8 and 7.0–8.0 (19H, m, aromatic).

(vi) *Methyl 3-(*o*-benzoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1f)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 441, 552, 696, 831, 885, 964, 988, 1023, 1072, 1111, 1151, 1184, 1219, 1305, 1346, 1385, 1472, 1595, 1701, 2910, 2950, 2989, 3048, 3411; ^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 3.0–3.6 (8H, complex m, aliphatic), 6.6–7.8 (24H, complex m, aromatic).

(vii) *Ethyl 3-(*o*-benzoxyphenyl)-2-(triphenylstannyl)propanoate (1g)* : IR ($\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) : 503, 552, 696, 831, 920, 964, 988, 1023, 1044, 1072, 1111, 1151, 1184, 1219, 1305, 1346, 1425, 1472, 1595, 1701, 2910, 2950, 2989, 3048, 3411; ^1H NMR (δ ppm) : 1.30 (3H, t, 3J 7.2 Hz, CH_3), 3.5–4.4 (7H, complex m, aliphatic), 6.8–7.8 (24H, complex m, aromatic).

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Kalita *et al.* : Steric effect in regioselective hydrostannation of alkyl *o*-alkoxycinnamates *etc.*

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